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MILESTONE REPORT

PROGRESS REVIEWED 3

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Agenda and draft minutes of board meetings available in document management system. Design report progress re-view and consolidation of contents in the form of a workshop with presentations on Indico (Green). Contributions for Open Access proceedings publication with SN (Gold) approved.

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Delivery Slip

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1. INTRODUCTION

Following its approval, the FCCIS project held its kick off meeting in November 2020, coupled to the 4th FCC physics week in the “FCC November Week 2020” (FCC NoW 2020). This meeting reviewed the challenges to deliver an implementation plan and a feasibility study for a new Research Infrastructure based on a new tunnel of ~100 km circumference, that could successively host an electron-positron (FCC-ee) and proton-proton collider (FCC-hh). The meeting, hosted virtually, offered numerous opportunities for cross-talks between the different scientific communities that are coming together under the FCCIS project. During FCC NoW the first FCCIS General Assembly meeting and Executive Board meeting took place, defining the key priorities and tasks for each of the project WPs and all participating members.

Since last Progress Reviewed report dated August 2022, the following events have taken place:

- **Final event of the international competition “Mining the Future”**, on 27 September 2022 at CERN’s Globe for Science and Innovation. The four shortlisted proposals have been presented to the public and the winner(s) of the competition were announced.
- **FCCIS 2022 Workshop**, 5-9 December 2022 at CERN, provided a forum for common discussion of FCCIS WP 2, 3, 4, 5 teams. The goal was also to discuss preparations for mid-term review with FCCIS team and other collaboration members.
- **6th FCC Physics workshop**, 22-27 January 2023 in Kraków, Poland.
- The ninth edition of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) Conference ‘**FCC Week 2023**’, 5-9 June 2023 in London, United Kingdom.
- **Industry meeting**, on 6 June 2023 as part of the FCC Week 2023, where selected professionals and young researchers offered an introduction of the FCC feasibility study and present projects in the fields of i) Civil Engineering, ii) Energy & Sustainability, iii) Accelerating Structures & Materials.
- **Early Career Researchers meeting**, on 8 June 2023 as part of the FCC Week 2023, aimed to bring together both ECRs working within the FCC community and those interested in the FCC to discuss experiences, hopes and concerns going forwards.
- **Review of CE and TI Requirements for FCC Experimental Sites**, 3-4 October 2022 at CERN. The goal was to review the surface and underground CE and TI requirements, implied by the principal detector concepts (in particular detector magnets and main support structures) of both FCC-ee and FCC-hh, for construction, installation, operation and maintenance phases.
- **Review of SRF Systems Layout with Associated CE and TI Concepts**, 3-4 October 2022 at CERN, to review the overall concept for RF system installation and evolution for FCC-ee, including the associated integration and technical infrastructure systems.

Table 1: Relevant project meetings during the period 01 August 2022 – 31 July 2023

Dates	Type of meeting	Venue	Attendance	Indico link
27/09/2022	Award ceremony	CERN	FCCIS community, MATEX experts, industries	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1182316/
5-9/12/2022	Workshop	CERN	FCCIS members, FCC Accelerators members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1203316/
22-27/01/2023	Workshop	Krakow (PL)	FCCIS members, FCC Physics community	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/

5-9/06/2023	Conference	London (GB)	FCC Community	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/
6/06/2023	Meeting	London (GB)	Industry	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1286813/
8/06/2023	Meeting	London (GB)	Early Career Researchers	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1280385/
3-4/10/2022	Review	CERN	Civil Engineering and Technical Infrastructure experts; FCC Scientific Advisory Committee	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1183771/
3-4/10/2022	Review	CERN	Radio Frequency and Technical Infrastructure experts; FCC Scientific Advisory Committee	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1184683/

2. FCCIS GOVERNANCE BODIES MEETINGS

2.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The General Assembly (GA) is the highest-level decision-making body in the FCCIS project. All the GA members are listed here: [FCCISGeneralAssemblyMembers < FCC < TWiki \(cern.ch\)](#)

The GA members have been requested to endorse the second instalment of the prefinancing that was due at the end of the first year of the project after submission of all deliverables and reports.

Organisation	Representative Full Name	E-mail	Phone	Date	Status
CERN	Michael Benedikt	Michel.benedikt [at] cern.ch	+41 22 767 3380	2020-09-24	Active
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MUL	Robert Galler	robert.galler [at] unileoben.ac.at	+43 664/2101607	2020-10-05	Active

Figure 1 – Screenshot of the Twiki page FCCIS General Assembly members

2.2. EXECUTIVE BOARD

The Executive Board (EB) implements the decisions of the General Assembly and proposes changes in the project and consortium plan to the GA, including changes of the CA and GA annexes.

The EB meets monthly, via the Zoom videoconferencing system. The EB consists of the Project Coordinator (PL and deputy), Work Package Leaders and their deputies.

The EB members are compiled at: [FCCIS Executive Board Members < FCC < TWiki \(cern.ch\)](#)

For each meeting, the agenda, list of participants and the minutes are posted in the Indico category [FCCIS Executive Boards · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#), with access restricted to the EB members.

10 Executive Boards meetings took place between August 2022 and July 2023 as shown in Table 2 :

Table 2: List of Executive Boards meeting during the period 01 August 2022 to 31 July 2023

Dates	Type of meeting	Venue	Attendance	Indico link
15/09/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1198018/
6/10/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1198019/
3/11/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1198020/
15/12/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1198765/
9/02/2023	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1245861/
9/03/2023	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1245863/
6/04/2023	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1245865/

3. FCC REVIEWS

3.1. REVIEW OF CE AND TI REQUIREMENTS FOR FCC EXPERIMENTAL SITES

A review of Civil Engineering and Technical Infrastructure requirements for FCC experimental sites took place at CERN on 3 and 4 October 2022. The meeting was restricted to presenters, invited experts and reviewers.

Figure 2 – Review of CE and TI requirements for FCC Experimental Sites
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1183771/>

3.1.1. Scope of the review

The FCC-ee and FCC-hh will feature two or four experimental detectors with associated surface sites. The underground structures and surface sites must satisfy all installation, operation and maintenance requirements, and accommodate the technical infrastructures required for the lepton and hadron collider experiments and for the accelerator.

3.1.2. Review goals and charge

The October meeting reviewed the surface and underground CE and TI requirements, implied by the principal detector concepts (in particular detector magnets and main support structures) of both FCC-ee and FCC-hh, for construction, installation, operation and maintenance phases.

- Assumptions:
 - Two or four experimental detectors for FCC-ee,
 - Locations in PA (Ferney) and PG (Charvonnex and Groisy) and/or in PD (Nangy) and PJ (Vulbens/Dingy-en-Vuache)
 - two primary and two secondary experiments for FCC-hh (PA, PD, PG, PJ)
 - single access shafts to all experimental caverns
 - addtl. access to exp. cavern via detector service cavern and service cavern shaft
- Detector for FCC-ee
 - Production, transport, assembly, and installation of detector support & magnet systems
 - Detector requirements on CE, cryo, gases, EL, CV infrastructure and computing
 - Cryogenic infrastructure system concept (installation, maintenance, etc)
 - EL, CV system concepts and integration
 - Readout electronics and data processing infrastructures
 - Operation, maintenance and safety requirements
- Detector for FCC-hh
 - Production, transport, assembly and installation of detector magnet system
 - Detector requirements on CE, cryo, gases, EL, CV infrastructure and computing
 - Cryogenic infrastructure system concept (installation, maintenance, etc)
 - EL, CV system concepts and integration
 - Readout electronics and data processing infrastructures
 - Operation, maintenance and safety requirements

- Requirements on civil engineering and surface sites
- Technical infrastructure evolution from ee to hh

3.1.3. Reviewers

Austin Ball (STFC), Peter Krizan (Jozef Stefan Institute), Rolf Lindner (CERN), Andrew Parker (University of Cambridge – Chairperson), Roberto Tenchini (INFN Sezione di Pisa), Frank Zimmermann (CERN – Secretary).

3.1.4. Agenda

Table 3 – Review of CE and TI requirements for FCC Experimental Sites agenda

Presentation title	Presenter(s)
FCC-hh detector concepts and requirements	Werner Riegler (CERN)
FCC-ee detector concepts and requirements	Mogens Dam (University of Copenhagen)
CE and TI requirements from the FCC-hh and FCC-ee detectors	Werner Riegler (CERN)
Civil engineering aspects and constraints	Timothy Watson (CERN)
Technical infrastructure aspects and constraints	Klaus Hanke (CERN)

3.1.5. Conclusions

The committee endorsed the baseline concept for the FCC experiment site underground structures consisting of an experimental cavern with a single experimental shaft for the main detector installation, linked via a transfer tunnel to the service cavern, with a second shaft, and connected via bypass tunnels to the machine tunnel on either side of the experimental area. This is an effective and efficient solution, taking into account the experience from LEP and LHC.

3.2. REVIEW OF SRF SYSTEMS LAYOUT WITH ASSOCIATED CE AND TI CONCEPTS

A review of SRF systems layout with associated Civil Engineering and Technical Infrastructure concepts took place at CERN on 3 and 4 October 2022. The meeting was restricted to presenters, invited experts and reviewers.

The screenshot shows an event page with the following details:

- Event Title:** Review of SRF Systems Layout with Associated CE and TI Concepts
- Logos:** Future Circular Collider logo on the left.
- Calendar Icon:** 3 Oct 2022, 14:00 → 4 Oct 2022, 17:00 Europe/Zurich
- Location Icon:** 30/7-010 (CERN)

Figure 3 – Review of SRF Systems Layout with Associated CE and TI Concepts
<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1184683/>

3.2.1. Scope of the review

Two long straight sections of the FCC shall accommodate the RF cryomodules for the two collider rings and for the full-energy booster. The baseline foresees single or multi-cell 400 MHz Nb/Cu and 800 MHz bulk Nb cavities, for the four different modes of operation. At the ZH and ttbar energies, the RF cavities are shared between the two beams, using electrostatic/magnetic separators for combination and separation. The booster could be installed either on top of the collider or in the same plane. The accelerator and RF layouts are linked

to the configuration of the cryogenic system, to tunnel diameter and add'l underground infrastructures, collider operation beam dynamics, physics etc.

3.2.2. Review goals and charge

The October meeting reviewed the overall concept for RF system installation and evolution for FCC-ee, including the associated integration and technical infrastructure systems. The following aspects were considered and addressed in the presentations.

- Baseline assumptions: for collider 400 MHz for Z, W, ZH and additional 800 MHz for tt, for the full-energy Booster always 800 MHz for all working points
- RF layout: all RF in PL, part in PL and in PH or part in PL and in PF (opposite to PL)
- RF general configuration options: all RF for collider in PL, all RF for Booster in PH or PF versus mixed variants (half voltage for collider and Booster in PL and in PH or PF)
- Operation sequence Z, W, ZH, tt
- Operation sequence starting with ZH, Z, W, tt
- 2 Kelvin part of cryo system
- Installation aspects
- Operation, maintenance, safety aspects
- Requirements on civil engineering from all above scenarios and impact and interaction with placement variants

3.2.3. Reviewers

Sergey Belomestnykh (FNAL), Erk Jensen (CERN, retired), Peter McIntosh (STFC – at most partly available), Andrew Parker (University of Cambridge – Chairperson), Thomas Peterson (SLAC), Laurent Taviani (CERN), Silvia Verdu Andres (BNL), Frank Zimmermann (CERN – Secretary).

3.2.4. Agenda

Table 4 - Review of SRF systems layout with associated CE and TI concepts agenda

Presentation title	Presenters
Running modes, RF Parameters, sawtooth, tapering, separation scheme, impedance, injection	Katsunobu Oide (KEK, Japan)
Setting the scene: Constraints and general layout	Klaus Hanke (CERN)
Integration for the RF Sections	Fani Valchkova
SRF layout, staging for different working points and other SRF aspects	Olivier Brunner (CERN)
Cryogenic aspects and constraints	Laurent Delprat (CERN)
Water cooling scenarios	Guillermo Peon (CERN)
Electrical power: grid connection, distribution, surface/underground splitting	Jean-Paul Burnet (CERN)
Civil engineering aspects and constraints	John Andrew Osborne (CERN)

3.2.5. Conclusions

The committee was content that the main issues had been considered by the project team and that the design was converging well, given the large number of interlocking technical issues which needed to be faced, and the need for more R&D in some areas. The committee noted the guidance from the CERN management that

the total power consumption should be evaluated, and solutions to minimize the load should be considered, including making use of waste heat.

4. FCC ANNUAL MEETINGS

The 6th FCC Physics Workshop took place in Krakow, Poland, from 22 to 27 January 2023.

<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/>

Figure 4 –6th FCC PW poster

The conclusions have been presented during the 9th edition of the FCC annual conference. The FCC Week 2023 took place in London, United Kingdom, from 5 to 9 June 2023.

Figure 5 – FCC Week 2023 poster

5. CONTRIBUTIONS FOR OPEN ACCESS PROCEEDINGS PUBLICATION

Together with Springer/Nature, a beneficiary of the FCCIS consortium, a publication has been released as an issue in EPJ Techniques & Instrumentation.

[Accelerating the design of the future circular collider | EPJ Techniques and Instrumentation \(springeropen.com\)](#)

This collection of articles describes progress on the Future Circular Collider (FCC) lepton (electron-positron) design as well as the hadron collider design, including aspects of machine-detector interface. The publication and has been based mainly on presentation that were given at FCC Week 2022 in Paris.

Figure 6: screenshot of the publication 'Accelerating the design of the future circular collider'